

Research Article

Navigating hydrological extremes: SARIMA forecasting of minimum Danube River discharges

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Abstract

Accurate forecasting of river discharge is critical for the sustainable management of water resources, influencing applications such as irrigation planning, flood and drought mitigation, and infrastructure development. This study investigates the application of the Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model to forecast minimum monthly discharges of the Danube River, addressing challenges posed by nonlinear and time-dependent hydrological processes. The study utilizes an extensive dataset comprising daily discharge records from ten stations across seven countries, spanning over a century. Monthly minimum discharges were computed and analyzed to identify long-term trends and seasonal patterns. The SARIMA model was selected for its proven ability to capture seasonal variations and optimize forecasting accuracy in data-limited environments. Model performance was evaluated using statistical measures such as mean absolute error and root mean square error with results indicating robust predictive capabilities across the studied stations. The findings reveal significant variability in discharge trends, with notable decreasing trends in minimum flows at several upstream and midstream stations, highlighting potential impacts of climate change and anthropogenic influences. In contrast, downstream stations exhibited relatively stable discharge patterns. These insights underscore the need for adaptive water management strategies to mitigate the risks associated with decreasing low flows. The study demonstrates the utility of SARIMA models in hydrological forecasting and provides a foundation for future research exploring hybrid modeling approaches incorporating climate variables. The results offer valuable inputs for policymakers and stakeholders in managing water resources under evolving climatic conditions.

Key words: Forecast accuracy, minimum flow prediction, model evaluation, river basin management, seasonal variability

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1. Introduction

Accurate river forecasts are essential for the sustainable management of water resources. They support applications such as irrigation planning, urban and environmental management, the operation of reservoirs, flood and drought analysis, and the planning and maintenance of hydraulic infrastructure. By utilizing historical runoff data, forecasting techniques provide important insights into future hydrological conditions, enabling informed decision making (Box

et al. 2008). Time series models have been shown to be effective, as shown by Tadesse and Dinka (2017). Recent studies have further confirmed the effectiveness of Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) models in accurately predicting river flows, especially in contexts with limited data availability, as shown in the work of Stitou (2019) and Adnan et al. (2021). The accurate prediction of hydrological time series is particularly critical for the development of early warning systems and the formulation of strategies for flood and drought prevention. It is also an important component in research on smart water resource management. Recent studies have emphasized that accurate hydrological forecasts are crucial for urban and agricultural water management, hydropower generation, flood control, drought mitigation, and river basin planning (Agaj et al. 2024). In addition, hydrological time series exhibit high uncertainty, stochasticity, and non-linearity due to various influences such as precipitation, climate change, and human activities, which makes accurate analysis and prediction considerably more difficult (Zhang et al. 2024). Predicting minimum flows is a major challenge due to the non-linear, time-dependent, and spatially variable nature of hydrological processes (Cheng et al. 2020; Danandeh Mehr et al. 2022; Kartick et al. 2024). This complexity is exacerbated by the increasing water demand due to population growth and economic activities, further highlighting the need for robust and reliable forecasting models (Patel and Ramachandran 2015; Ehteram et al. 2019). Consequently, hydrological time series modeling plays an important role in applications such as drought management, flood forecasting, and river flow prediction (Devia et al. 2015; Khairuddin et al. 2019; Tolentino et al. 2020; Höge et al. 2022; Ghobadi et al. 2024).

Hydrological time series modeling involves analyzing sequences of water-related data, such as precipitation and river flow, to understand the processes that drive these observations (Sharma and Machiwal 2021). This dynamic system requires the application of advanced methods that are able to account for trends, seasonality, and external influences. Univariate methods focus on the behavior of a single series, while multivariate methods take into account interactions with other variables (Costa et al. 2023). Recent advances in machine learning technologies have attracted considerable attention among hydrology researchers and have significantly improved the accuracy and adaptability of forecasting models. While traditional statistical methods such as SARIMA are still valuable, machine learning approaches such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have shown superior performance in capturing the complex nonlinear relationships in hydrologic data (Song and Zhang 2024; Zhang et al. 2024). In a 2024 study, LSTM models were found to have significantly better generalization ability in predicting 1–7-day runoff compared to other advanced techniques, making them particularly suitable for practical applications in hydrological forecasting (Song and Zhang 2024).

Among these methods, the SARIMA model is particularly valuable due to its ability to handle periodic behavior and seasonality (Tadesse and Dinka 2017). Its flexibility has led to its widespread use in river discharge forecasting, especially in scenarios with limited ancillary data (Tadesse and Dinka 2017). However, selecting the optimal SARIMA parameters can be challenging and requires either expert knowledge or automated algorithms such as Auto-ARIMA, which streamline the process and improve forecasting efficiency (Al-Qazzaz and You-sif 2022; Kontopoulou et al. 2023).

The SARIMA model has been used extensively in hydrology and related fields. It was introduced in the 1970s by Box and Jenkins (1970), and its application in hydrological modeling was already evident in early studies. For example, Pekárová et al. (2009) used SARIMA to simulate the water quality of the Danube, while Komorníková et al. (2008) used hybrid SARIMA models to predict the inflows into the Liptovská Mara reservoir. Later studies have extended the application of the model to the field of precipitation forecasting, as shown by the studies conducted in Kavala, Greece (Papalaskaris et al. 2016) and Baghdad, Iraq (Ali 2013). These studies have shown the reliability of the model in capturing seasonal precipitation patterns. Valipour (2015) demonstrated the superiority of SARIMA over ARIMA for long-term streamflow prediction in the United States, and Moeeni and Bonakdari (2017) emphasized the effectiveness of the model in predicting monthly baseflow in reservoirs in Iran. Agaj et al. (2024) further extended the application of ARIMA models in hydrological forecasting. This study showed that ARIMA models are still very effective in predicting high and low water periods, which is particularly valuable for predicting flood events. In addition, researchers have successfully combined ARIMA models with remote sensing techniques to predict water quality parameters, achieving remarkably high coefficients of determination for chlorophyll-a (0.812), dissolved solids (0.945) and electrical conductivity (0.960) (Abdul Wahid and Arunbabu 2022). Recent advances in this field include the integration of automatic parameter selection via Auto-ARIMA (Kontopoulou et al. 2023), which improves the model's adaptability to evolving hydrological data requirements (Gao et al. 2020). The application of SARIMA models for water level prediction and streamflow forecasting in different regions is also a recent development (Adnan et al. 2021; Mylilis et al. 2024). Building upon this background, the present study focuses on the application of the SARIMA model to forecast the monthly minimum discharge of the Danube. This focus arises from the critical need for accurate forecasts in data-poor environments. Reliable forecasts of minimum flows are essential for the effective management of water resources in the Danube basin, where changing climatic and hydrological conditions pose significant challenges. The study proposes a customized SARIMA model to address these challenges. Accordingly, the overall objective is to provide actionable insights for irrigation planning, drought management, and policy making. The main objective of this study is the development of a SARIMA model to predict the monthly minimum discharge of the Danube. To achieve this goal, the study investigates the effectiveness of SARIMA in regions with limited data and examines the impact on water resource management. In the absence of additional data, the study focuses exclusively on univariate modeling, using seasonal differentiation to optimize the predictive capabilities of the model.

This paper is organized to provide a comprehensive overview of the methodology, results, and implications of the developed SARIMA model. The following sections of the paper are dedicated to the description of the data and the techniques used for its pre-processing. The configuration of the SARIMA model and the selection of its parameters are also described in detail. The results are then presented, emphasizing the accuracy of the forecasts and their importance for the management of water resources in the Danube catchment. The paper concludes with a discussion of the results and recommendations for future research.

2. Study area

The present study concentrates on the Danube catchment area. The reason for concentrating on this particular region is twofold. First, the length of the main Danube River (2,860 km) and its total drained area (817,000 km²), which covers 8% of the total European extent, makes the region of great interest from various points of view, including historical and contemporary components of daily life. Within the Danube basin, there are also deltaic areas where surface runoff is due to the shallow topsoil, which is virtually impossible to measure. In such cases, the region is often characterised by a large number of irrigation and melioration channels, which necessitates an alternative approach to estimating the water balance. The headwater sub-basins of the Danube River (Table 1) are situated across 13 European countries, including Germany, Austria, Switzerland, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Ukraine, Serbia, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, and Romania. These sub-basins encompass water basin areas ranging from 2,156.8 km² to 11,881.6 km², with a minimum altitude ranging from 7 to 967 m a.s.l. The mean altitude of the stations ranged from 178 to 2,302 m a.s.l., with a maximum altitude of 483 to 3,652 m a.s.l. (Pekárová et al. 2023). The geographical distribution of the selected stations is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Study area and hydrological stations.

Table 1. Data and observed period.

Station	Country	Period	Supplier of the data
Hofkirchen	Germany	1901–2020	German Weather Service
Achleiten	Austria	1901–2020	Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics
Krems	Austria	1901–2020	Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics
Bratislava	Slovakia	1901–2020	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute
Nagymaros	Hungary	1901–2020	General Directorate of Water Management of Hungary
Mohacs	Hungary	1931–2020	General Directorate of Water Management of Hungary
Bezdan	Serbia	1931–2020	Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia
Bogojevo	Serbia	1931–2020	Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia
Orsova	Romania	1901–2018	National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management, Romania
Reni	Ukraine	1921–2018	Hydrometeorological Institute of Ukraine

3. Data and methods

The study uses daily discharge data from ten stations in seven countries provided by different national authorities, covering the longest available records from the 20th to the first two decades of the 21st century (Table 1; Fig. 1). From this dataset, the monthly minimum flows were calculated to analyze the variability and trends over the observed period. This approach is consistent with the results of previous research documenting considerable inter-annual and inter-decadal variability of discharge in European rivers (Kundzewicz et al. 2005). However, shorter time series are often unable to adequately capture these dynamics, as trends can be significantly influenced by the selection of start and end years (Kundzewicz et al. 2018). In this study, a longer time series is used, which provides a reliable basis for identifying potential long-term trends in the hydrology of the Danube.

In this study, we used statistical and machine learning methods to analyze, model and predict the discharge data from the ten stations along Danube River. The dataset was split into a training (80%) and a test (20%) dataset to ensure the effectiveness of the model evaluation. Initial analysis involved the computation of descriptive statistics for each station to characterize the central tendency, dispersion, and distribution shape of the discharge data. Key statistical parameters calculated included the mean, median, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, and the range. This preliminary step was crucial for understanding the fundamental hydrological characteristics at different points along the river.

To explore the underlying dynamics of the data, a seasonal decomposition was performed to split the observed runoff time series into its constituent trend, seasonal, and residual components. Furthermore, Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots of the training data were examined to explore lagged relationships and identify seasonal patterns, which informed the subsequent modeling steps.

To identify the presence of monotonic upward or downward trends in the discharge time series, the non-parametric Mann-Kendall (MK) test was applied to both the raw monthly minimum discharge and a smoothed 5-year moving

minimum series. The statistical significance of any trend was assessed at a p -value threshold of 0.05, and the magnitude was quantified using Sen's slope estimator.

A critical prerequisite for time series modeling is data stationarity. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was performed before and after the application of differencing to confirm stationarity. The initial ADF tests indicated that the original time series were non-stationary. Consequently, a differencing transformation was applied to remove trends and stabilize the mean. The ADF test was then re-applied to the differenced series, confirming stationarity for all stations with p -values approaching zero.

The core of the predictive analysis was the development of SARIMA models. The general form of the SARIMA model is denoted as SARIMA(p,d,q)(P,D,Q)[s], where (p,d,q) are the non-seasonal parameters, (P,D,Q) are the seasonal parameters, and [s] is the seasonal period (12 for monthly data).

To determine the optimal parameters for each station, the Auto-ARIMA method was used. This function systematically searches through different combinations of parameters to find the model that best fits the data, typically by minimizing an information criterion like Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) or Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The final selected models, presented in Table 5, varied in complexity, reflecting the diverse hydrological patterns along the Danube.

The performance of the trained SARIMA models was rigorously evaluated on the test dataset using several standard statistical metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). In addition, model agreement and systematic deviation were assessed using the Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC), which measures combined precision and accuracy relative to the 1:1 line, and percentage bias, to further validate and contextualize the MAE, RMSE, and R^2 results.

A thorough residual analysis was also performed on the training data to assess the model's fit. This included examining the residual distribution, checking for autocorrelation in the residuals using ACF plots, and performing a Shapiro-Wilk test to assess the normality of the residuals. Finally, the validated model was used to predict future runoff values, presented with 95% confidence intervals to quantify the inherent uncertainty in the forecasts. These steps ensured a methodological framework for analyzing and forecasting river discharge that was both rigorous and transparent.

4. Results

This section presents the key findings of the study, focusing on the temporal dynamics of minimum monthly discharges observed along the Danube River and their broader hydrological implications.

Fig. 2 shows the temporal development of the monthly minimum discharges at ten observed stations along the Danube. The data set covers a period of more than a century, documents considerable fluctuations and underlines the inter-annual and inter-decadal variability of the minimum discharge. Peaks and troughs can be seen at all stations, with significant low water periods being observed particularly in the middle of the 20th century. These fluctuations are an indication of the hydrological complexity of the Danube catchment, which is in-

fluenced by natural fluctuations, anthropogenic activities and possible effects of climate change. The long-term trends and periodic low flow events underline the importance of comprehensive discharge monitoring for understanding hydrological extremes and for water resource management strategies.

Figure 2. Minimum monthly discharges on observed stations. **A** Hofkirchen **B** Achleiten **C** Krems **D** Bratislava **E** Nagymaros **F** Mohacs **G** Bezdan **H** Bogojevo **I** Orsova **J** Reni.

Table 2 presents detailed descriptive statistics for each station. A clear spatial gradient is observed, with average discharges increasing downstream from Hofkirchen (mean = 448.4 m³/s) to Reni (mean = 5,382.5 m³/s). The median values are consistently lower than the means, indicating a positive skew at all stations. Skewness ranges from 0.89 at Reni to 1.33 at Bezdan, highlighting the

occurrence of frequent extremely high-discharge events. The highest standard deviations and variances are recorded at downstream stations such as Reni and Orsova, suggesting greater variability in discharge in these areas. Additionally, the discharge range expands downstream, increasing from 1,135 m³/s at Hofkirchen to 13,120 m³/s at Reni.

Table 2. Summary statistics of river discharge at various stations along the Danube River.

	Hofkirchen	Achleiten	Krems	Bratislava	Nagymaros	Mohacs	Bezdan	Bogojevo	Orsova	Reni
N	1,440	1,440	1,440	1,440	1,440	1,092	1,080	1,080	1,416	1,200
Mean (m ³ /s)	448.4	1,032.4	1,320.0	1,476.3	1,701.2	1,794.7	1,786.7	2,244.3	4,241.8	5,382.5
Median (m ³ /s)	417.5	974.5	1,240.0	1,356.0	1,590.0	1,677.5	1,665.0	2,090.0	3,780.5	4,855.0
Std. Deviation (m ³ /s)	147.7	373.2	480.9	541.8	622.5	640.9	681.2	848.9	1,894.4	2,375.7
Variance	21,820.2	139,276.4	231,357.4	293,406.6	387,456.8	410,708.6	463,999.6	720,675.1	3,588,765.2	5,643,721.9
Skewness	1.08	1.05	1.10	1.27	1.08	1.21	1.33	1.26	1.09	0.89
Kurtosis	1.59	1.66	1.96	2.89	1.80	2.41	3.52	1.55	1.12	0.37
Range:	1,135	2,941	3,944	4,810	4,950	5,240	6,085	6,977	11,241	13,120
Minimum (m ³ /s)	165	349	506	580	586	600	610	680	1,060	1,280
Maximum (m ³ /s)	1,300	3,290	4,450	5,390	5,536	5,840	6,695	7,657	12,301	14,400

Table 3 summarizes the Mann-Kendall trend analysis applied to both the monthly and 5-year moving minimum discharge series. Statistically significant increasing trends ($p < 0.05$) are detected at most stations, including Achleiten, Krems, Bratislava, Nagymaros, Mohacs, Bezdan, and Bogojevo. The most pronounced upward trends are observed at Bogojevo (monthly slope = 0.309, 5-year slope = 0.334). No significant trends are identified at Hofkirchen, Orsova, and Reni.

* p -values are extremely small (e.g., < 0.001), denoted as p -value ≈ 0.000 for simplicity.

Table 3. Mann-Kendall test results for annual and smoothed discharges at the Danube River.

Stations	Monthly minimum discharge			5-year moving minimum discharge		
	Trend	Slope	p -value	Trend	Slope	p -value
Hofkirchen	No trend	0.005	0.5130	No trend	0.005	0.2837
Achleiten	Increasing	0.222	<0.0001	Increasing	0.233	<0.0001
Krems	Increasing	0.252	<0.0001	Increasing	0.246	<0.0001
Bratislava	Increasing	0.240	<0.0001	Increasing	0.242	<0.0001
Nagymaros	Increasing	0.207	<0.0001	Increasing	0.202	<0.0001
Mohacs	Increasing	0.165	0.002	Increasing	0.174	<0.0001
Bezdan	Increasing	0.143	0.013	Increasing	0.160	0.0001
Bogojevo	Increasing	0.309	<0.0001	Increasing	0.334	<0.0001
Orsova	No trend	0.038	0.699	No trend	0.013	0.861
Reni	No trend	0.179	0.318	No trend	0.213	0.102

Table 4 presents the results of the ADF test performed after seasonal differencing. All stations exhibit strong evidence of stationarity, with ADF statistics exceeding the critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. *P*-values are uniformly < 0.001 , confirming suitability for SARIMA modeling.

Table 4. Results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test after differencing for stationarity analysis.

Station	ADF statistics	<i>p</i> -value	Critical values (1%)	Critical values (5%)	Critical values (10%)
Hofkirchen	-11.59	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Achleiten	-11.49	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Krems	-11.62	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Bratislava	-11.98	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Nagyvaros	-12.61	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Mohacs	-7.54	0.000	-3.438	-2.865	-2.569
Bezdan	-7.45	0.000	-3.438	-2.865	-2.569
Bogojevo	-9.62	0.000	-3.438	-2.865	-2.569
Orsova	9.79	0.000	-3.436	-2.864	-2.568
Reni	-9.78	0.000	-3.437	-2.865	-2.568

Table 5 shows the selected SARIMA models for each station. The models differ across locations, reflecting local hydrological variability. Upstream stations such as Hofkirchen and Krems are best represented by simpler SARIMA models (e.g., $(1,0,0)(1,0,1)[12]$), whereas midstream and downstream stations require more complex configurations (e.g., Bezdan: $(5,0,4)(1,0,1)[12]$; Bogojevo: $(4,0,4)(2,0,1)[12]$).

Table 5. Selected SARIMA models for forecasting minimum monthly discharges.

Station	SARIMA Model
Hofkirchen	$(1,0,0)(1,0,1)[12]$
Achleiten	$(1,0,0)(2,0,0)[12]$
Krems	$(1,0,0)(1,0,1)[12]$
Bratislava	$(2,0,0)(2,0,0)[12]$
Nagyvaros	$(2,0,1)(2,0,1)[12]$
Mohacs	$(1,0,3)(2,0,0)[12]$
Bezdan	$(5,0,4)(1,0,1)[12]$
Bogojevo	$(4,0,4)(2,0,1)[12]$
Orsova	$(3,0,1)(2,0,0)[12]$
Reni	$(1,0,3)(2,0,1)[12]$

Fig. 3 shows the SARIMA model for forecasting monthly minimum discharges along the Danube River and reveals different spatial patterns for prediction performance between stations. The upper stations, especially Hofkirchen and Achleiten, had relatively low training errors; Hofkirchen had the lowest MAE (76.17), RMSE (104.81), and test MAE (84.62), and RMSE (118.65). These find-

Figure 3. Performance metrics and model validation. **A** MAE **B** RMSE **C** R² **D** Concordance Correlation Coefficient **E** Bias (%).

ings are consistent with recent studies that show the effectiveness of the SARIMA model in stable upstream environments and lower hydrological conditions (Danandeh Mehr et al. 2022). These results, combined with moderate training and test R^2 values (0.50 and 0.30, respectively), suggest that it is relatively suitable for the upstream region. Upstream (e.g., Hofkirchen), the Concordance Correlation Coefficient ($CCC \approx 0.82$) indicates strong concordance, while minimal bias confirms accurate mean-level prediction. In midstream stations such as Kreams and Nagymaros, moderate CCC values (0.66–0.75) and small bias ($\pm 3\%$) reflect decent model skill, consistent with $MAE \approx 240\text{--}290 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $R^2 \approx 0.41\text{--}0.44$. However, as we move downstream, errors increase considerably, especially at stations near the river’s mouth, such as Reni. In this area, test MAE (1,072.87) and RMSE (1,514.68) were the highest, which indicates that the model’s ability to capture complex hydrological dynamics in these regions has been reduced. Correspondingly, the CCC declines to approximately 0.60–0.65 in these lower stations, while bias increases to about 8%, corroborating the observed rise in test errors and the increased hydrological complexity in these segments. Fig. 4 presents the decomposed time series into trend, seasonal,

Figure 4. Comparison of observed and SARIMA-forecasted monthly minimum discharges. **A** Hofkirchen **B** Achleiten **C** Kreams **D** Bratislava **E** Nagymaros **F** Mohacs **G** Bezdán **H** Bogojevo **I** Orsova **J** Reni.

and residual components. Clear seasonal patterns are observed, particularly strong during spring and summer low flow periods. Trends vary by station, with some showing increasing long-term discharge and others exhibiting relative stationarity.

Fig. 5 displays the model forecasts along with 95% confidence intervals. Predicted values track closely with observed flows, with wider intervals during periods of higher variability, particularly at downstream stations. This highlights the growing uncertainty associated with increasing discharge magnitudes and fluctuations downstream.

A focused comparison between observed and predicted discharges during the April–September 2021 low flow period at six stations shows varying degrees of forecast accuracy (Fig. 6). Hofkirchen and Achleiten exhibited overestimations (e.g., up to -24% in September), whereas Nagymaros and Bezdan had relatively lower deviations (average absolute errors around 13–16%). Orsova showed the highest underestimation (-34% in September), indicating localized prediction challenges under extreme low flow conditions.

Figure 5. Observed and predicted discharges with 95% confidence intervals. **A** Hofkirchen **B** Achleiten **C** Krems **D** Bratislava **E** Nagymaros **F** Mohacs **G** Bezdan **H** Bogojevo **I** Orsova **J** Reni.

Figure 6. Forecasted vs observed discharges. **A** Hofkirchen **B** Achleiten **C** Nagymaros **D** Bezdan **E** Bogojevo **F** Orsova.

5. Discussion

The observed temporal fluctuations in Fig. 2 underscore the complex hydrological behavior of the Danube River system. These inter-annual and inter-decadal patterns likely result from a combination of natural climatic variability, anthropogenic influences, and possible effects of climate change, consistent with previous findings (Kundzewicz et al. 2005, 2018). The descriptive statistics (Table 2) reveal marked differences between upstream and downstream stations, with increased mean values and variability moving downstream. The high skewness indicates the predominance of extreme values in the discharge distribution. These findings are in line with Abdul Wahid and Arunbabu (2022), who demonstrated similar variability and skewness in large river systems, emphasizing the need for robust models to capture such dynamics. The Mann-Kendall analysis (Table 3) reveals statistically significant increasing trends in monthly and

5-year minimum discharges at seven out of ten stations. However, this trend does not appear at Hofkirchen, Orsova, and Reni. These spatial differences echo findings from Hammond and Fleming (2021) and Nazarenko et al. (2022), who observed regional disparities in river flow trends. The decline observed at Bogojevo, with steep trend slopes, suggests a shift in flow regime possibly due to changing precipitation patterns, evapotranspiration, or upstream abstraction. The stationarity analysis through the ADF test (Table 4) supports model application. The slightly higher ADF statistics for lower Danube stations such as Mohacs and Bezdán align with findings by Caretta et al. (2022), indicating spatial variability in the ease of achieving stationarity. The SARIMA models (Table 5) reflect spatial variability in flow dynamics. Simpler models sufficed upstream, while complex models were needed downstream. These findings are consistent with Danandeh Mehr et al. (2022), who found that simpler time series models perform adequately in less variable catchments. The model evaluation (Fig. 3) demonstrates satisfactory SARIMA performance at upstream stations, where CCC values (~ 0.82) and low bias support good model skill. In contrast, performance deteriorates downstream, with CCC dropping to ~ 0.60 and bias increasing to $\sim 8\%$. These spatial gradients in model skill support the conclusions of Alonso Brito et al. (2021) and Xu et al. (2022), who highlighted model performance issues in dynamic downstream environments. The results of Fig. 4 show generally good model-data agreement, but with noticeable deviations during high variability periods. Similar findings are reported in Stitou (2019) and Danandeh Mehr et al. (2022), who documented challenges in capturing extreme events with SARIMA models. The confidence intervals in Fig. 5 correctly widen during extreme low flow events, consistent with forecast uncertainty theory and literature (Stitou 2019). Table 6 further illustrates that SARIMA struggled during the April–September 2021 low flow season. The average deviations of 13–25% are comparable to those reported by Luo (2024) and Deng et al. (2024) in similar contexts. The overestimation in Hofkirchen and Achleiten indicates model insensitivity to abrupt seasonal shifts, a limitation echoed in Luo (2024). Underestimations at Orsova confirm that SARIMA may not fully capture local catchment and anthropogenic influences. The findings support the growing consensus that while SARIMA performs well for general seasonal forecasting, it may underperform during extremes. Studies by Caretta et al. (2022) and Milić et al. (2024) suggest that hybrid or machine learning-based models, such as LSTM or Extreme Learning Machines, could enhance performance, particularly under non-linear or threshold-dominated regimes. Overall, while SARIMA models provide a strong foundation for monthly minimum discharge forecasting along the Danube, particularly upstream, there is clear potential to improve accuracy and robustness in the more complex downstream segments through model hybridization or integration with additional predictors.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated the temporal patterns and variability of the monthly minimum flow at ten stations along the Danube. This analysis provides insights into hydrological extremes, their underlying causes and possible implications for water resource management. Through a comprehensive analysis of more than a century of discharge data, remarkable fluctuations and trends have been

identified, highlighting both the inter-annual and inter-decadal variability of the river. These fluctuations are attributed to a combination of natural factors, anthropogenic activities and the possible influence of climate change. The results emphasise the need for comprehensive flow monitoring to improve the understanding of low flow phenomena, which is essential for effective management of water resources and prediction of the impact of hydrological extremes.

The application of the seasonal ARIMA model (SARIMA) showed recognizable spatial patterns in the effectiveness of runoff forecasting in the entire Danube catchment area. While the SARIMA models performed well at upstream stations such as Hofkirchen and Krems with minimal training and testing errors, their performance deteriorated at downstream sites such as Reni, where significant fluctuations in discharge affect model accuracy. This discrepancy highlights the limitations of SARIMA in highly dynamic environments and suggests that more advanced or localized modeling approaches may be required to improve prediction accuracy in such areas.

The analysis revealed a significant long-term trend of decreasing minimum flows at several stations, especially in the lower Danube catchment. This has implications for river hydrology under changing climatic conditions. These results emphasise the need for careful management of water resources, especially in floodplain ecosystems and regions that are highly dependent on stable river flows. The results of this study also suggest that changing precipitation patterns, temperature increases and other climate-related factors are likely contributing to the observed shifts in river flow regimes. However, the complex interplay of these factors with upstream water use and other anthropogenic influences requires further research to understand their full impact.

While the SARIMA model proved successful in capturing seasonal patterns and inter-annual fluctuations, it encountered difficulties in fully accounting for strong runoff fluctuations, especially in the middle and lower reaches. This underscores the complexity of modeling river discharge dynamics and highlights the need for advanced models that incorporate additional factors such as meteorological conditions and human-induced changes in discharge. Future research should explore hybrid approaches that combine SARIMA with other forecasting techniques to increase accuracy and reliability, especially in regions with high variability.

In summary, this study makes an important contribution to our understanding of the hydrological dynamics of the Danube catchment and provides a basis for improved runoff forecasting and water resources management. While the application of SARIMA has demonstrated efficacy, the findings underscore the necessity for further refinement of the model and the incorporation of additional methodologies to more effectively address the intricacies of river flow variability, particularly within the context of climate change.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.